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ANALYSING THE OPERATION OF THE CONCEPT OF RULE OF LAW FOR NIGERIA'S DEVELOPMENT

Appolos Dimas, Adamu Adamu Jauro***

ABSTRACT

Since independence and the enthronement of democratic norms, constitutionalism and the rule of Law in Nigeria, good governance and national development has remained a mirage. Nigeria's nationhood is largely bereft of ideas, lack of development, arbitrariness and the insulation of the people's rights and privileges as enshrined in the constitution. This article examined the concept of rule of law and constitutionalism in Nigeria. The paper also discussed the concept of democracy and good governance. The article further interrogates the relationship between democracy and good governance in Nigeria. It was found that a country may be practicing democracy and yet there may be no good governance and development. It was also found that even though Nigeria has been practicing democracy, there is no substantive development largely due to lack of adherence to the principle of rule of law and constitutionalism. The article also discussed some of the critical governance problems in Nigeria. The article then concluded by making some suggestions on how rule of law and constitutionalism can engender progress and development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Rule of Law, Nigeria, Constitution, Democracy, Constitutionalism.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The preamble to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 as amended expresses the firm and solemn resolve of Nigerians to engender among others, “good government and welfare of all persons...on the principles of freedom, equality and justice...¹ The Constitution further provides that the Nigerian State is “based on the principles of democracy and social justice”. The Constitution acknowledges the fact that “sovereignty belongs to the people of Nigeria from whom government through the Constitution derives all its powers and authority”²

However, our nation has recently witnessed the distressing consequences of workers enduring agonizing hardships stemming from irregular or non-payment of wages. Thousands are dying on our bad roads due to the deplorable condition of the roads; erratic power supply to households and industries, poor medical facilities and constant industrial actions has bedeviling our educational system. All these are due to bad governance in our constitutional democracy.

Since independence, Nigeria has been grappling with the issue of rule of law, constitutionalism and good governance. In fact, most of the problems facing the country today is traceable to poor leadership with poor understanding of the principle of rule of law and constitutionalism. This paper explores the role of the hallowed principle of rule of law and constitutionalism in the enthronement of democracy and good governance in Nigeria and charts a course of action consistent with the imperative of transforming our democracy.

To achieve this, the paper is divided into four parts; The first part examines the concept of rule of law and constitutionalism. The Second part will examine the indicators of good

*LL. B (Hons), LL.M, BL. and PhD in view. A Lecturer with the Nigerian Law School, Yola Campus. Email: dimazgubezz@yahoo.com

** LL. B (Hons) BL, Lecturer with Federal Polytechnic Kaltungo, Gombe State. Email: adamuaj@gmail.com

¹ Emphasis is ours.

² Section 14(1) (2) (a) CFRN,1999. Emphasis is mine

governance and how national development can be achieved in a constitutional democracy. The third part deals with the concept of democracy and good governance in Nigeria, and the problems of governance in Nigeria. The last part concludes with observations and recommendation.

2.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is based on the doctrinal method of research. It involves analyzing the statutory provisions and cases by applying reasoning to power³. It involves analysis of statutory and case law, arranging, ordering and systematizing legal propositions through legal reasoning or rational deduction. This includes the use of primary and secondary materials. Thus, in collecting materials for this study, we relied on statutes, case laws, online materials as well as web information gathered from the site of relevant institutions.

3.0 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The work will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. How effective is the rule of law in enhancing the development of Nigeria?
2. What are the impediments to the actualization of rule of law and development in Nigeria?

4.0 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This research aims to analyze the concept of rule of law in promoting Nigeria's development. In doing so, the research will seek to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To examine the concept of rule of law and national development in Nigeria.
- ii. To examine how effective is the rule of law in national development.
- iii. To look at some of the reasons why despite the practice of rule of law in Nigeria there is still under development and bad governance.

³ Gaisokwu, M, '*Legal Research and Methodology*' A-Z of Writing thesis and Dissertations in a Nutshell' (Jos: Fab Anieh, 1994) p.14

5.0 CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATION OF THE RULE OF LAW AND CONSTITUTIONALISM

The rule of law is one of the most invoked concepts in legal and political discourse. Yet, as pointed out by a distinguished jurist, “[a] though a notion of considerable antiquity, the concept of ‘Rule of Law’ has provoked such passionate academic disputations that up till the present moment, its precise import is yet enveloped in a web of controversy.”⁴

The concept of the Rule of law is an important one in constitutional democracy. Constitutionalism, as a practice, is the fall out of the rule of law and is the exercise of government powers and the definition of the relationship of governmental organs inter se and with the citizen according to constitutional rules. To a large extent, constitutionalism is synonymous with the rule of law which itself simply refers to the requirement that all powers of government be exercised according to the law and not arbitrarily, with adequate safeguards against abuse of government powers and free access to an independent and impartial judiciary that guarantees fair trial.⁵ The Rule of Law is thus defined as that which provides that all men (and women) are equal before the law and the functions of state officials and their actions are subject to review by ordinary courts. Government power is to be exercised according to law. No offender is to be punished except in accordance with the law applied prospectively by ordinary courts observing the due process of law. The rule of law is the supremacy of the will of a popular, legitimate and democratic constitution over the arbitrary will of State officials and private persons.⁶ In reality, there is no fundamental dichotomy between constitutionalism and the rule of law.

The rule of law is a concept that is predicated on the supremacy of law over the unregulated and arbitrary will of a government. It is an ideal rooted in constitutionalism. The concept of the rule of law has been formulated in many ways, both broad and narrow, and there is much disagreement on the values and principles it is supposed to engender.

Dicey, an English constitutional expert of great repute, formulated an exposition of the concept of the rule of law which has become classic. To Dicey, the rule of law means the

⁴ C.C, Nweze, *Judicial Integrity: Desideratum for Good Governance in a Democracy* Jos Bar Journal [2003] Vol 9

⁵ S.I Nchi, *Separation of Powers under the Nigerian Constitution* Green world Publishing Company Ltd 2000

⁶ *ibid*

absolute supremacy of regular law as opposed to the influence of arbitrary power; a man can be tried and punished only according to the law. The concept also means the equality of all persons and authorities before the law administered impartially by ordinary courts of law and the subjection of all persons to the ordinary law of the⁷.

According to Dicey:

(The Rule of Law) means, in the first place, the absolute supremacy or predominance of regular law as opposed to the influence of arbitrary power, and excludes the existence of arbitrariness, of prerogative, or even of wide discretionary authority on the part of the government...it means, again, equality before the law, or the equal subjection of all classes to the ordinary law courts; the 'rule of law' in this sense excludes the ideal of any exemption of officials or others from the duty of obedience to the law which governs other citizens or from the jurisdiction of the ordinary tribunals.⁸

Thereafter, theories of the concept of the rule of law have evolved from Dicey's theory.⁹ The most fundamental principle in Dicey's theory is that the government is subject to the law and may exercise its powers only in accordance with the law. Where a government claims to be above the law and not subject to any constitutional restraint, such government is not under the rule of law but arbitrary and capricious rule of state officials.

In his enunciation of the concept of the rule of law and constitutionalism, Professor Wade takes the view that law must back every act of the governmental power affecting the rights, duties and obligations of the citizenry. Accordingly, the rule of law demands that:

- i. For any act to be valid it must be in accordance with the law;

⁷ ibid

⁸ A.C Dicey, *The Law of the Constitution*, pp.202-203

⁹ Harvey, "The Challenge of the Rule of Law" [1961]59 Mich L.R. 603; Friedman, "The State and the Rule of Law in Mixed Economy" [1971]; Dworkin, "A Matter of Principle" [Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1986], Raz, "The Rule of Law and its Virtue" (1977) 93 LQR195; Hay, et al. *Abion's Fatal Tree* [Harmondsworth; Penguin 1977], Allan, "Legislative Supremacy and the Rule of Law"

- ii. Government activities must be conducted within the bounds of defined rules and regulations;
- iii. Disputes involving legality of government actions must be decided by courts of law without executive interference;
- iv. There should be no undue privileges and discriminations in society; and
- v. No one should suffer punishment outside the law.¹⁰

Another author Dennis Lloyd¹¹ perceives the rule of law as imposing those procedural guarantees that have been found necessary to ensure what American constitutional practice referred to as the “due process of law”. This involves matters such as:

- i. Ensuring the independence of the judiciary;
- ii. Providing for the speedy and fair trial of accused persons and for adequate judicial control over police and police methods of securing confessions from accused persons;
- iii. Provision of adequate safeguards regulating arrest, detention and trial;
- iv. Provision of adequate legal aid for those whose finances are insufficient to secure suitable legal services;
- v. Protection from self-incrimination.

The rule of law is dynamic in consequence of which it has shifted from its neutrality as regards the content of legal rules and is now concerning itself with the distribution of power in society and how to solve problems of inequality, social injustice and bad governance. The need to remove economic, political, cultural and other forms of social injustice demands that a constitution should assist not merely in checking arbitrariness and abuse of power but also in the provision of structures that will build a free, just and egalitarian society.

¹⁰ Professor Wade, “Administrative Law” in Abiola Ojo, *Constitutional Law and Military Rule in Nigeria* (Ibadan Evans Brothers, 1987) p.241

¹¹ Dennis Lloyd, *The Idea of Law* (London: Penguin Books, 1964) pp.161-164

6.0 DEMOCRACY

Democracy as propounded by the American icon, Abraham Lincoln, which has found its root in several countries in the world, has certain basic tenets without which it loses its character as a democracy. These attributes which could be regarded as the essential ingredients of democracy are: Rule of Law, Constitutionalism, Fundamental Human Rights, independence of the judiciary and the freedom of Press.¹² Any society established on the above tenets has always been described as democratic. Conversely any society devoid of the rule of law, constitutionalism, guaranteed fundamental rights; freedom of the press and independence of the judiciary towards the attainment of justice is largely undemocratic and fertile ground for tyranny, despotism and dictatorship. It follows therefore that a democratic society is a recipe for development politically, socially, legally, economically, educationally, culturally etc. it will be devoid of the rule of men and rule by force of arms or oppression, injustice and tribal banality. Prejudices will wither away and give birth to a nation where peace, justice, freedom and equality reign supreme.¹³

7.0 THE CONCEPT OF GOOD GOVERNANCE

The benchmark or yardstick for measuring development in a democratic world is the concept of good governance¹⁴. The most important word in this concept is the word “governance”. Governance means how people are ruled and how the affairs of the state are administered and regulated. It also means a nation’s system of politics and how it functions in relation to public administration and law. Therefore, the concept of good governance goes beyond that of “government” to include political dimension.¹⁵

The goodness of governance is open to interpretation of the experience of the governed relative to the performance of the leader within a political entity. According to the United

¹² D.D Dodo, “*A virile Bench/Bar. A recipe for sustaining democracy and the Rule of Law.*” A paper presented at the 2005 law week ABU Zaria on 23 June, 2005

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Adedoyin Akinsulore, “Democracy, Good Governance, Rule of Law and Executive Arm of Government in Nigeria” A Journal of Contemporary Legal and Allied Issues (2015) IFJT Part 2 (May-August) ISSN 0794-1

¹⁵ Landell-Mill and Serageldin, Proceedings of the World Bank Annual Conference on Development Economics 1991 (World Bank, 1992, 304).

Nation Development Programme (UNDP),¹⁶ Good Governance is the exercise of economic, political and administrative authority to manage a country's affairs at all levels. It comprises of the mechanisms, processes and institutions, through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their legal rights, meet their obligations and mediate their differences. It is a legitimate, accountable and effective way of obtaining and using public power and resources in the pursuit of widely accepted social goal.¹⁷ This however, has to be distinguished from the term 'governance' which simply means the process of decision making or the process by which decisions are implemented (or not implemented). It is a process where by public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources, and guarantee the realization of human rights.¹⁸ By extension, good governance accomplishes all the foregoing in a manner essentially free from abuse and corruption and with due regard to the rule of law and constitutionalism.

The concept of good governance often emerges as a model to compare ineffective economies or political bodies, with viable ones.¹⁹ This is achieved by taking into cognizance the existence or non-existence of some good governance indicators such as accountability, transparency, rule of law, constitutionalism, political stability, Government effectiveness and the management of corruption.

Good governance has fundamental influence on the quality of lives of the citizens. it is the basis for sustainable and strong democracies, it creates conditions in which governmental institutions, markets, private enterprises, civil societies and organizations functions.²⁰

8.0 INDICATORS OF GOOD GOVERNANCE

There are basic indicators of good governance. Some of these indicators are: participation, due process, consensus oriented, transparent, accountable, responsive, effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive, and the rule of law. It minimizes corruption, the views of minorities are taken into consideration, the voices of the most vulnerable in the society are

¹⁶ Government for sustainable Human Development, A. UNDP POLICY PAPER, Pg. 2-3

¹⁷ United Nation's Millennium Goals (MDGs) < <http://www.Un.org/millenniumgoalsaccessed> > accessed 9 December 2018

¹⁸ What is governance? < <http://www.state.gov/secretary> > accessed 9 December 2018

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Kofi Anan Inaugural speech as UN Secretary General, July,1997 @ < <http://www.gdvc.org> > accessed 10 December 2018

heard and taken into consideration in decision making. It is responsive to the present and future needs of the society.

a. Participation

Participation²¹ could either be direct or through legitimate immediate institution or representative. Participation needs to be informed and organized. This means freedom of association and expression on the one hand. It is argued that for a well-informed participation to concur, some form of transparency is necessary, but not sufficient; it has also been argued that those most affected by the decision should have the most say, while those that are least affected should have the least say in the matter.²² Participation in activities may be motivated from an administrative or citizen perspective. Viewing from the administrative point, participation can build public support for activities, it can also facilitate useful information exchange regarding local conditions. From the perspective of the citizen, participation enables individuals and groups to influence agency's decisions in a representational manner.²³ In this sense, it allows for the redistribution of power to enable the poor citizens, presently excluded from the political and economic processes, to be included.²⁴

Participation is important in governance because there is a growing across the society that State cannot direct the actions of the citizens without their cooperation whether in matters dealing with public health concerns, climate change or tackling terrorism because we are in an era where progress is only possible if individuals are willing to contribute to the solution. For this to be achieved, public participation is essential.

Public participation is not only important to government, but also to individuals, because it has the potentials to change how individuals and communities live and interact. Taking part

²¹ Participation is an informed, autonomous and meaningful involvement of an individual or community in empowering decision making and action—regarding political economic, management or other social decisions.

²² Glass, JJ " *Citizens Participation in Planning: the relationship objective and technique*" *Journal of American Planning Association* 45(2) 1979-180 retrieved, 2010, 06-12

²³ *ibid*

²⁴ Arnstein, S.R " *A ladder of citizen participation*" *Journal of American Planning Association* 35(4)©1996)216-224

in local decision making can have a transformative effect on how people think about themselves and their role in the society generally.

b. Accountability

Accountability is a vital requirement of good governance. Not only government institutions but also private and civil organizations must be accountable to the public, and to the relevant stakeholders. In general, an institution or organization, is accountable to those who will be affected by its decision or action. Accountability can only be enforced where there is transparency and the rule of law. Accountability is one of the pillars of an open society. It ensures fairness, economic equality and civic participation.²⁵ It is also a key to economic prosperity. This is based on the fact that due to lack of accountability in the players in economy, stakeholders may lose the confidence they have in it, and will become reluctant to put in their best. The more accountable a government is, the more likely it is that the results of performance measurement are going to be true and fair representative of the performance being measured.²⁶ For some developing countries, lack of accountability may lead to fall in the participation rate in their development programs by the citizens, a situation that may lead to further deterioration in the development process.²⁷

Accountability is therefore no doubt, a very important pillar of governance. Without it, the problems of governance will be hard to defeat. With it, the confidence of stakeholders increases. It is achieved through faithfulness in various aspects of governance.

c. Due Process

Due process as a term, is capable of wide application²⁸. In ordinary parlance, it means strict application of laid down rules. However, as it applies to the public sector, due process implies that government activities and businesses can be carried out openly, economically and transparently without favoritism and corrupt tendencies.²⁹

²⁵ Governance and Accountability; Open Society foundations-OSF available @ www.sorros.org

²⁶ Corporate Social Responsibility; Accountability and Governance. Available @ www.greenleaf.publication.com

²⁷ *ibid*

²⁸ See for e.g., Constitutional Due-Process, which presupposes strict application of rules under the Constitution.

²⁹ Ezekwesili O. (2005) "Due process Mechanism and Digital Opportunities" being paper presented to the University, Community at Prince Alexandria, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Due process may also be construed as a mechanism that certifies for public funding only those projects that have passed the test of proper implementation, packaging and that adheres stringently to the international competitive approach in the award process.³⁰ In the management of public finance, due process is not necessarily a new concept and indeed does not create any radical changes in the existing rules. Due process represents a new consciousness which ensures that existing rules of conduct for public officers as laid down in various financial regulations and other laws affecting public finances are strictly implemented.

d. Equity and Inclusiveness

Another basic indicator of good governance is equity and inclusiveness. This requires that all groups in society be given equal opportunity to improve and maintain their well-being. It means giving an open door to all and treating all equally and all should enjoy benefits derivable from the government.

9.0 DEMOCRACY AND GOOD GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA.

It is conceivable, however, that in euphoria and optimism, one may forget that democracy, though unarguably the best form of government for any nation, it is also the most difficult to manage. Democracy, it should be remembered is not a plotted plant which can be transplanted into any soil and grown without work or effort. This was aptly put by Professor Sam Oyovbaire as follows:

*The problem of democracy revolves around how to forge a development process which is simultaneously participatory for individual citizens, sensitive to, and protective of individual rights, freedoms and liberty; accommodative of multiple and competitive loyalties; and generative of economic growth and distributive justice.*³¹

The impact of the above is that non-democratic states like Saudi Arabia, Japan, China, etc., are even more stable even though, democracy is not practiced there. It is obvious to ask

³⁰ Obasanjo O. (2004) "Due process saves Nigeria N 104 billion. Thisday, Nigeria.

³¹ Oyobaire Sam, "Problems of Democratic Transition. Guardian" June, 1999.

here whether democracy can be synonymous with good governance. The answer no doubt, is in the affirmative. Thus, democracy in most Third World Countries including Nigeria is antagonistic to good governance. For instance, the problem of Nigeria is even more confounded by the absence of free and fair elections. The conduct of free and fair election is an important cornerstone of democracy and good governance. Once a government whose legitimacy is questioned or once a government comes into power through an election that is not free and fair, such a government operates without being accountable to the people.³²

Good governance is a bye product of democracy that is adjudged free and fair.

The reason why good governance has been a mirage in Nigeria is because the political leaders do come into power through a process that is not free and fair. Therefore, since the process is not free and fair, there is no accountability because the mandate was not freely given to them by the Nigerian people.

10.0 CRITICAL GOOD GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS IN NIGERIA

a. Leadership Problems

Nigeria's fundamental approach to leadership is troubling. In Nigeria, the primary aim for aspiring for leadership position is self-centered. Whereas Nigerian Leaders have the power to educate, inspire, and provide people with the resources to advocate for the cause they believe in, but like parents, they have failed in their responsibilities to lead by good examples.³³ Chinua Achebe in his book³⁴ concludes that Nigeria's problem is bad leadership and evidence on ground has consistently shown that he is correct. It is leaders who are self-centered and not the poor rural dwellers that are responsible for Nigeria's underdevelopment.

Leading a country involves making policies and finding solution to the myriads of problems, ensuring stability of the polity, and guiding the society to prosperity.³⁵ However, large number of the political leaders in Nigeria lack vision, the passion, and character to

³² Uya, E.O "The Democratic Project in Nigeria" (1999), Calabar, CATS Pub Ltd.

³³ Lanre Olu-Adeyemi, "The Challaenges of Democratic Governance in Nigeria" *International Journal of Business and Social Science VOL.3 No.5 March 2012*.

³⁴ The Trouble with Nigeria, Heineman Educational Publishers 1998.

³⁵ Ibid (n) 32

effectively govern the state and deal with the ailing economy. They do not have a clear understanding of their responsibilities aside satisfying themselves. They are only good at drumming the country's problems without finding solutions.

b. Recruitment Process

One of the major challenges of democratic governance in Nigeria lies in the process of electing public officers into leadership positions. The President and Vice President at the federal level; the Governor and Deputy Governor at the State level; and the Chairman and Councilors at the Local Government Level and all the members of the National and State Houses of Assembly are all recruited through the process of an election. However, it is sad that the electoral process and the political party system are corruption ridden and not sufficiently participatory.³⁶

The elections are not only flawed but warped, the political parties are dominated by godfathers, money bags and ex-military leaders, and their primaries (if ever conducted) are mostly selective, non-participatory and undemocratic.³⁷ Thus resulting in the corruption of the leadership, loyalty to god-fathers rather than to the people, indifferent to the electorate in their style of governance and lack of accountability.

c. Corruption

Corruption is another major challenge to good governance in Nigeria, corruption has, among others been defined as an act of "requesting, offering, giving or accepting directly or indirectly a bribe or any other undue advantage or the prospect thereof, which distorts the proper performance of duty or behaviour required of the recipient of the bribe, undue advantage of the prospect thereof".³⁸ Unfortunately, long after independence, Nigerian leaders still harbor the mentality that public money belong to no one and that any person who has access to it should convert it into his personal use.

³⁶ Azinge Epiphany, "Law, Money and Politics" Epiphany Press, 2004.

³⁷ Lanre Olu-Adeyemi, "The Challaenges of Democratic Governance in Nigeria" *International Journal of Business and Social Science* VOL.3 No.5 March 2012.

³⁸ Kofele-Kale, "The International Law of Responsibility for Economic Crimes: Holding State Officials Individually Liable for Acts of Fraudulent Enrichment" *Hampshire, England: Ashgate Publishing Ltd. 2006.*

d. Ethnicity

Nigeria is the most populous black country in the world with diverse cultural heritage. The country has a population of over 200 million with not less than 250 ethnic groups. Nation building has been complicated by Nigeria's tremendous diversities, thus, making the management of diversities to be more central than ever as a problem in Nigeria's political process. Leaders in Nigeria see leadership as an opportunity to empower their ethnic communities rather than the entire nation. Appointments are done not on merit but on the basis of ethnic inclinations.

11.0 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the article examined the meaning and concepts of constitutionalism, rule of law and good governance and how they affect democracy and good governance in Nigeria. The work also identified some key elements of good governance and some of the governance challenges in Nigeria. It is found that for democracy and good governance to thrive in Nigeria, there must be strict adherence of constitutionalism and rule of law. Leaders must be held accountable, the recruitment process that is non participatory must also be changed through a further amendment of the Electoral Act to engender inclusiveness of all the citizenry in the democratization process that will be for the common good of all Nigerians and not a section.